

RESEARCH ARTICLE

2025, vol. 12, issue 2, 81-89
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17870661>

SELF-DETERMINATION AMONGST ONLINE LEARNING STUDENTS RECEIVING INSTITUTION SUPPORT AT A NAMIBIAN DISTANCE LEARNING INSTITUTION

Anna-Marie NANGOLO¹
Lydia MBATI²

¹ Centre for Innovation in Learning and Teaching, University of Namibia, Namibia,
ORCID: 0009-0007-7617-4444

² Institute for Open and Distance Learning, University of South Africa, South Africa
ORCID: 0000-0002-1182-2654

Abstract

Literature has established that soft skills are required in the ever-changing world of work. Student self-determination has proven to have a positive impact on student retention and success. In a distance learning institution in Namibia, attrition rates have been high, with higher than average numbers of students either dropping out or performing poorly in their online learning programmes.

Using a qualitative research approach, this study sought to determine the Institution's online learning students' experiences regarding self-determination using Ryan and Deci's (2000) Self-Determination Theory. Data were analyzed using Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis (IPA), a qualitative research method that emphasizes participants' perspectives and lived experiences. The study used thematic analysis to understand the relation between self-determination and institutional support online students enrolled in a Bachelor of Education course receive.

The findings revealed students who managed their time effectively, funded their own studies possessed more self-efficacy, motivation and resilience. However, challenges of poor tutor engagements, internet connectivity, physical limitations, financial support and poor motivation increased the possibilities for dropping out.

Keywords: Online learning, student support, attrition, higher education, self-determination, motivation, phenomenology

Introduction

The constantly changing world of work due to technological innovation requires graduate students who possess skills that go beyond memorization, predictable tasks, market research and other tasks that can be replicated by human-machine learning and Artificial Intelligence. Soft-skills have increasingly gained recognition amongst Standards Generating Bodies as essential in the world of work (Imane Messaoudi & Sana Sakale 2024; Kaushik & Sinsinwar 2024) calling for the development of these interpersonal skills among graduates seeking to join the workforce. Humans' psychological needs, motivation, and well-being are shown to interact in various settings via Self-Determination Theory (SDT) (Hsu, Wang and Levesque-Bristol 2019). According to SDT, individuals have greater motivation and engagement during activities, when their requirements are being met, better supported and satisfied (Ryan & Deci 2020). Self-Determination Theory (SDT) prioritises individuals' innate motivating tendencies for personal development and acquisition of knowledge, as well as the factors that facilitate such tendencies. Rotar (2022) postulates that autonomy means self-regulating one's actions or endeavours, with competence being the capacity to complete tasks effectively, while relatedness provides a sense of belonging. SDT predicts positive functional results in motivation, self-regulation, learning, organisation and integration, vitality, and well-being and that students are able to complete their online courses if they receive adequate online support. It also links intrinsic motivation to autonomy, competence, and relatedness which are needed in an online learning. The argument posits that the fulfilment of fundamental psychological needs is of utmost importance to course design to boost intrinsic motivation, engagement, and retention. Online learning depends on user

motivation and how courses are organised. In MOOCs, self-determination theory explains how humans act with agency, volition, and engagement (Deci, Ryan 2000). Self-determination theory explains how interest and enjoyment are fostered or hindered, therefore, it is used in a MOOC design (Khan et al. 2018). It postulates that humans are intrinsically agentic and information-seeking, with a natural urge to learn about themselves by taking in their surroundings and incorporating what they find into an existing identity. Intrinsic motivation is crucial in MOOCs because entry barriers are low compared to traditional schooling (e.g., no course fees). SDT stresses "choice, decision, and commitment" (Khan et al. 2018). This study investigated student autonomy and motivation through the perspective of self-determination theory (Ryan, Deci 2020).

The Research Context

Bachelor of Education in Organizational Learning and Development (BOLD) is a new three-year programme replacing Bachelor of Education in Lifelong Learning and Community Education because of the curriculum transformation process at a Namibian Distance Learning Institution (NDLI). The former two faculties, namely the Faculty of Education and the Faculty of Human Sciences (FEHS), were merged to establish the School of Education and Human Sciences, which is one of the four faculties at the learning institution. Diplomas and bachelor's degrees are offered at the undergraduate level, while Masters and Doctoral degrees are available at the graduate and postgraduate levels. All students who started the degree in 2022 and were in their third year by 2024 were eligible to participate in this study.

Research Framework

Self-Determination Theory (SDT) represents a framework for understanding human motivation and personality. It integrates conventional empirical techniques with an organismic metatheory, emphasising the significance of innate human resources in fostering personality growth and behavioural self-regulation (Ryan, Kuhl, & Deci, 1997). Therefore, the focus is on examining individuals' natural growth inclinations and fundamental psychological requirements that underpin their self-motivation and personality cohesion, along with the circumstances that promote these beneficial processes. Online education's independence and flexibility match Self-Determination Theory (SDT). Students in online learning have more control over scheduling, location, and learning materials. Additionally, implementing SDT in online student support is justified by its proven ability to boost motivation and engagement (Chiu 2022). The SDT framework facilitates the development of students' inherent motivation by promoting autonomy, competence, and relatedness (Deci & Ryan 2000). Students have different requirements, preferences, and self-regulation, therefore, SDT allows Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) to tailor support services to each student's requirements. SDT provides a solid and comprehensive paradigm for comprehending and improving the online learning environment. The Self-Determination Theory (SDT) is crucial in online education, as it helps educators create effective environments for students. The theory posits that individuals have three inherent psychological needs: autonomy, competence, and relatedness. It has been extensively examined and implemented across various domains, highlighting its vast and critical usefulness in online education.

Figure 1: Self-Determination Theory (Ryan & Deci, 2000)

The ideas of SDT are strongly aligned with the characteristics of online education, which include independence and flexibility (Chen & Jang 2010). In virtual learning environments, students frequently possess more agency in determining the timing, location, and way they interact with educational materials. Nevertheless, the increased independence can present difficulties, hence emphasising the importance of applying Self-Determination Theory (SDT) even further. An examination of the literature on SDT highlights both the merits and constraints of this theoretical framework. On one hand, SDT has garnered empirical support and has made significant contributions to the comprehension of human motivation in various circumstances (Ryan & Deci 2000). The emphasis placed on autonomy and intrinsic motivation has exerted significant influence on the development of educational and clinical practises (Ikahihifo et al., 2019; Johansen et al., 2023; Pineda et al., 2024; Wisniewski et al., 2018). According to SDT's viewpoint, all students possess an inherent inclination towards acquiring knowledge, achieving expertise, and establishing relationships with others but they need nurturing conditions such as student support, multimodal techniques, teaching methods and strategies that suit all student needs, and proactive learning settings (Vansteenkiste et al. 2018). Additionally, SDT is seen as a learner-centred active learning approach to increase motivation (Bogunović et al., 2023; Jenó, 2015), while also enhancing grit and satisfaction (Lozano-Jiménez et al., 2021). SDT's influence on student retention and wellbeing is also referenced in literature (Li et al., 2020; Zak-Moskal & Garrison, 2021), highlighting the various positive affordances offered by the theory to teaching learning and student retention.

Literature Review

This review presents an analysis of research conducted in the field of self-determination theory by several authors over the past decades.

Pineda et al. (2024) report on a study which sought to examine the relationships between interpersonal style of teacher autonomy support, basic psychological needs satisfaction, autonomous motivation and depressive symptoms of a group of university students, through a structural regression model. Data collection occurred using a questionnaire that was administered to university students. The results indicated the teacher's interpersonal style of autonomy support positively predicted the satisfaction of basic psychological needs and this the autonomous motivation; but negatively depressive symptoms (Pineda, Lozano-Jimenez & Moreno-Murcia 2024).

Frühauf, Sagmeister and Kopp (2023) conducted a study to aimed to describe barriers to and opportunities for integrating climbing, as a form of adventure education, in Austrian school physical education. Using a qualitative research approach, the study determined that adventurous activities boost happiness by allowing people to be in touch with nature and satisfy fundamental psychological needs. Because autonomy, competence, and social relatedness—the three pillars of SDT—develop most rapidly throughout adolescence, including adventure sports into existing programmes may be an effective way to intervene during this formative period (Dahl, Allen, Wilbrecht and Suleiman 2018). Also, the 1985 Deci and Ryan Self-Determination Theory (SDT) is a motivational framework for studying social and motivational factors that affect face-to-face beginners' running group participation (Johnson, Cronin, Huntley, and Marchant 2022). Sport psychology researchers use it as a major theoretical approach (Ryan & Deci 2017b). On a continuum, SDT suggests six different orientations of motivation. Among these perspectives on regulation are amotivation, environmental, introjected, identifiable, integrated, and intrinsic. Similarly, a study examined the effects of RunSmart, a 10-week beginner running programme, on motivation, attendance, and well-being (Johnson, Cronin, Huntley, and Marchant 2022). SDT was employed henceforth. With regards to Next Generation Science Standards (NGSS), the self-determination theory was employed as a critical perspective to analyse how these factors can influence students' perception of autonomy, expertise, and integration with the broader society (Winburn 2023). To succeed socially and emotionally, these students need regular face-to-face contact with adults as stated by (Ladson-Billings 2021). As a culturally and economically varied population of students, they require educational systems that can accommodate their varying needs and abilities (Chiu 2022). Focusing on science and engineering practices and crosscutting concepts should help students make independent judgements in the future is a primary goal of the Next Generation Science Standards according to (Winburn 2023). As a result of their technological reliance in the classroom and their lack of intrinsic motivation, SDT can be utilised to address these issues (Chiu, Sun and Ismailov 2022). To improve students' personal motivation and academic results, SDT educators advocate for less authoritarian classroom settings and more needs-supportive ones (Ryan & Niemiec 2009). Similarly, Shogren, Anderson, Raley and Hagiwara (2021) describe use of self-determination theory in the realm of intellectual and developmental disability (IDD). They emphasised that creating opportunities for all students to develop self-determination in inclusive settings has the potential to improve goal attainment for all students, including those with IDD (Shogren, Scott et al. 2021). Furthermore, Raley, Shogren et al. (2021) postulated that the impact of an evidence-based strategy is meant to increase student self-determination by aligning the causal agency theory to Self-Determined

Learning Model of Instruction (SDLMI). The results found that self-determination allows students to self-reflect and learn more about their ability to make decisions, engage in actions toward a self-selected goal, and strengthen their beliefs about their capacities to achieve significant goals (Raley, Shogren et al. 2021).

The universality of SDT is evidenced in the various contexts illustrated in which SDT has been studied; physical education, conventional classrooms, diverse classrooms, and among intellectual and developmentally disabled students. This study added the study of SDT in an online learning context within the African context to the literature.

Method

A transcendental phenomenological study aims to explore the how distance students experienced self-determination in this qualitative study. Data was collected using semi-structured face-to-face interviews. Interviewees are selected using purposive sampling. According to Creswell J (2019), phenomenological studies use personal experiences to describe how many people understand a term or phenomenon. Qualitative research is needed for this study's focus on online learners' perspectives and experiences (Creswell & Poth 2018).

Approximately 31 students were registered, therefore, 8 participants are selected using purposive sampling with inclusion/exclusion criteria. The program is offered at three Campuses across Namibia. Table 1 shows the geographical location of students who participated in the phenomenological study.

Table 1: Geographical location of the study participants

Campus	Number of students registered
Windhoek	3
Oshakati	2
Rundu	3

The researcher interviewed students on three campuses in person. This study employed semi-structured interviews, which involved using predetermined, open-ended questions to allow the researcher to gather additional information at different points and to obtain clarification from students. Thematic analyses were employed to report findings of the research. The aim of the study was to explore the lived experiences of online students enrolled at the institution regarding their self-determination.

Findings

Based on the analysis of the interview transcripts, the frequency of themes aligned with Self-Determination Theory (SDT), appear in table 2.

Table 2: Findings from student interviews on Self-determination (SDT)

		Participatin...	Totals
		8 419	
SDT - Competence	4 23	23	23
SDT - Engagement	6 14	14	14
SDT - Persistence	5 20	20	20
SDT - Relatedness	3 24	24	24
SDT - Volition	5 21	21	21
SDT -Autonomy	8 32	32	32
SDT -Creativity	3 16	16	16
SDT -Enhance Performance	3 18	18	18
SDT -Motivation	8 40	40	40
Totals		208	208

Experiences of Self-determination

Theme 1 - Autonomy

Participants felt significant autonomy in overseeing their academic pursuits, underscoring the importance of online education's flexibility. 100% of the students perceived themselves as responsible for their own learning and conveyed a sense of confidence in their ability to complete and handle all academic tasks needed. Most participants exhibited a favourable perspective regarding their studies and expressed intentions to advance to the

subsequent degree of education. All participants felt sufficiently encouraged during orientation and by their instructors to thrive in their studies and graduate on time. Additionally, many participants reported that they encouraged one another via WhatsApp groups by, for instance, reminding one other about impending task and organising study groups. Below are some of the snippets from Nvivo coding:

Participants Ps01 said:

"It also helps when you create WhatsApp groups where you share information with others. If you don't understand something you can ask other students to explain as lecturers don't answer phones in their offices"

Participants Ps04 said:

"We share on the WhatsApp e.g. maybe if a student does not understand the module. As a group of students, we come together and try to help each other, to make each other understand, share experiences that we have. Everyone also tries their best make sure that they download study guide or any relevant resources"

Participants Ps08 said:

"Once the classes start, especially the first lesson, the lecturers motivate us very much"

Theme 2 - Competence

In this theme, a multitude of students (100%) exhibited confidence in their capabilities and qualifications, crediting this to the resources and support offered by the educational institution, as well as their intrinsic ability to attain necessary qualifications, graduate, enhance their life, and advance their studies. Apart from circumstances, including one person who had a loss in the family, all other participants believed they possessed the competence to submit assessments punctually and succeed in examinations. All students commenced their registration in 2022 and are currently in their third year of study, indicating that they possess the qualifications to graduate next year.

Participants Ps03 said:

"Yeah, I will complete it and graduate, I want to become better in life"

Participants Ps07 said:

"Now things are improving as they arrange classes through zoom/teams and Big Blue Button"

Participants Ps06 said:

"Yeah, like for me, I feel like everything is fine. I study on my own. Yeah, I think I'm self-motivated, I study by myself. I decided what time to study and what time to rest"

Theme 3 - Relatedness

100% of the students experienced a sense of belonging and connection through interactions with peers and educators, despite the digital context. Most participants indicated that their interactions with classmates and professors have enhanced due to technological advancements, such as the creation of WhatsApp groups, whereas they previously experienced feelings of isolation.

Participants Ps06 said:

"Yeah, we like for us we have we learn in group we are three where we choose which time in which day to go study together and do our tests and assignment and other assessment, so we think we just push each other to go through"

Participants Ps07 said:

"With the Module specific What's app group, we share information about the course such as questions you don't understand, notes on a topic, reminder about the due date etc"

Participants Ps01 said:

"It also helps when you create WhatsApp groups where you share information with others. If you don't understand something you can ask other students to explain as lecturers don't answer phones in their offices"

Self - Determination Fosters

Theme 4 - Volition

All students (100%) demonstrated an inner motivation to pursue objectives and make choices that correspond with their values and interests. Despite recognising the limitations associated with online learning, all participants remain committed to fulfilling the requirements of this program and advancing their studies upon graduation.

Participants Ps03 said:

"My performance is very good because I passed my first year and they passed my second whereby I only failed on one module. I used to submit my assignment every time before the due date even"

Participants

Ps04

said

'I am trying to learn, to get something as I have told you that I want to apply what I learn to my work. The chances are very low that I won't get that post, so I am always applying and if I get a chance, I will do what I have learned. I must study, learn something and put it practice and make difference in somebody's life. Okay, I have passed all my modules except for the research that is left. I think my learning performance has been good throughout'.

Theme 5 – Motivation

All students (100%) felt considerable motivation and resolve to achieve success, driven by individual goals and institutional backing. The levels of motivation varied, with some students demonstrating significant drive due to the relevance of their courses to their career goals and the practical application of their studies, while others depended on moral support, such as encouragement from peers, to achieve effectively. For many participants, self-determination encompassed both the innate motivation of students to excel, and the motivation acquired from instructors to achieve performance. Participant motivation surfaced as a significant factor from the interviews done with participants. All students (PSO1-PSO8) indicated high levels of intrinsic motivation, empowering them to tackle any obstacle. Participants acknowledge that online students encounter several obstacles and hurdles; nonetheless, they remain steadfast in their determination to persist and complete their education. Participants are motivated by their successful attainment of the diploma level, having surmounted numerous hurdles, and are determined in their pursuit of honours level study. The quality of service for online students has markedly enhanced, and participants are determined to utilise technology capabilities to fulfil their goals. Below are the snippets of the type of difficulties faced by participants in Nvivo:

Participants Ps01 said:

"I finished my Diploma and then I enrolled for the bachelor's degree"

" Online/learning allows me to work and study at the same time"

Participants Ps05 said:

"I will make it; I already completed the Diploma on my own and I was motivated to start with the degree afterwards. I think I'm motivated to achieve anything I want. I'm very excited about that. I want motivation that we get when you are studying, to get something for yourself and from school or from the university. You are being motivated by others. And I'm working very hard to get that"

Participants Ps08 said:

"If this continue well and I graduate after next year, I aim to enroll for Honours degree as well because I can study and work at the same time"

Theme 6 - Engagement

Engagement levels remained predominantly high, while some students actively participated in online discussions and WhatsApp activities, as they recognised that marks were awarded for participation (100%). However, some encountered difficulties in maintaining consistent engagement, particularly when faced with network and data issues.

Participants Ps08 said:

"As distance students we are expected to work on our own. When I come back from work, I relax a bit, eat dinner with family and then I take out my books to study"

Participants

Ps06

said:

"I read whenever I get time especially at night, so far, I have passed all the exams"

Participants Ps05 said:

"I want motivation that we get when you are studying, to get something for yourself and from school or from the university"

Outcomes of Self-Determination

Theme 7 - Enhanced Performance

All participants recognised the positive support and motivation they received, which led to improved academic performance 100%. They credited their success to structured support, including skills development, involvement in community projects, and relationship building via WhatsApp. Available resources included the uploading of lecture notes intended for full-time students, PowerPoint presentations, study guides, and assignment letters.

Participants Ps03 said:

"Yeah, I will complete it and graduate, I want to become better in life"

Participants Ps06 said:

“My performance is not that bad. It's not that good. I'm just in the middle of average”

Theme 8- Persistence

A notable sense of tenacity was evident (100%), as students showed resolve to overcome challenges and achieve their academic goals despite facing obstacles.

Participants Ps01 said:

“I finished my Diploma and then I enrolled for the bachelor’s degree”

Participants Ps08 said:

“I have a timetable with assignment due dates, so I need to make sure that I meet all my due dates except when it’s an emergency like death in the family. I always work on my own”

Participant Ps06 said:

“Yeah, I do. I do submit my assignment on time and others activity, and everything is going well. So far, no difficulties

Theme 9 - Creativity

The level of creativity varied (100%) among students; some were motivated to embrace unconventional thinking and utilise innovative techniques relevant to their work context, thereby flourishing in their creativity, while others felt restricted by the online format and believed they needed to do only the bare minimum to fulfil requirements and pass the module. Most participants acquitted creativity with overall academic performance.

Participants Ps08 said:

“I’m creative when it comes to activities that need to be done in the community. I always take a lead to guide especially when there are few resources”

Participants Ps05 said:

“I use what I learn from work to add to my assignments, I dont just read from the internet. The examples I use are from my work to show that I understand both the theory and practical work”

These findings highlight the importance of institutional support in fostering self-determination among online learners, hence improving performance, persistence, and innovation.

Figure 4.1 visualisation of interview result with students (SDT)

The visualisation on self-determination illustrates findings pertaining to students' online learning. Student motivation is fundamental to online learning, as evidenced above. All themes related to self-determination are essential in online learning.

Discussion

The study revealed that students who improved their academic performance through effective time management and online platforms, while financing their tuition via their businesses, exhibited better performance outcomes. Self-efficacy, or the belief in one's abilities, significantly influences motivation and resilience (Pumptow & Brahm 2021). Autonomy and motivation are interconnected elements; both are essential for success in online learning. The predominant support phases were observed among students. A considerable proportion of

undergraduate's encounter difficulties in sustaining motivation and completing their degrees successfully. Several students faced challenges, including insufficient tutor engagement, poor internet connectivity, and feelings of isolation, which negatively impacted their performance, aligning with the findings of researchers such as Berry & Hughes (2020), Stephen, Rockinson-Szapkiw & Dubay (2020), and Kamer & Ishitani (2019). A considerable proportion of undergraduate's encounter difficulties in sustaining motivation and completing their degrees successfully. The continuation of distance learning is notably influenced by individual circumstances and the availability of support networks. Students with strong familial and institutional networks exhibit higher persistence rates. However, challenges such as technological issues and reduced motivation may hinder ongoing effort. Creativity is a vital element in Self-Determination Theory and constitutes a significant factor. Some students contend that the flexibility of distance learning enhances creativity; however, the structured online framework may sometimes hinder this creative process. The investigation of online learning indicates a division in student experiences; some value its flexibility and innovative theoretical applications, while others identify limitations imposed by its rigid structure. The study recommend that lecturers enhance online learning by adopting the flipped classroom model, which divides the learning process into preparatory activities prior to class and instructional engagement during class sessions. This method facilitates student engagement with knowledge, allows for response acquisition, and improves comprehension. The implementation of a flipped classroom enhances intergroup interaction, thereby promoting the generation of new ideas through collaborative discussions. This method enhances student participation in creative subject matter, resulting in an engaging and interactive educational environment hence promoting student self-determination.

Conclusion

This study emphasises the complexity of student experiences in online learning environments, particularly through the lens of Self-Determination Theory (SDT). While autonomy empowers many students by granting them freedom and control, it also presents significant challenges, such as feelings of isolation and frustration due to delayed feedback and support. Competence, as evidenced by students' confidence in managing academic tasks, is crucial for their persistence and success; however, technological barriers hinder progress for some individuals. Relatedness, defined as the sense of belonging, was identified as the most deficient aspect of the online experience, with students often feeling disconnected from their peers and instructors. Despite these challenges, students demonstrated significant motivation driven by personal goals, career aspirations, and institutional support, which enhanced their dedication to academic pursuits. Active participation in interactive learning activities enhances engagement and improves academic performance, highlighting the importance of fostering connection and interaction in online education. The findings highlight the need for enhanced support systems to foster autonomy, competence, and relatedness in online learning environments, thereby promoting student satisfaction and success.

References

- Bogunović, B., Jovanović, O., Simić, N. and Mutavdžin, D., 2023. *Self-Determination Theory Perspective on Motivation and Solo Performance among Students in Higher Music Education in Serbia*. Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences University of Rijeka.
- Chen, K-C & Jang, S-J. 2010. Motivation in Online Learning: Testing a Model of Self-Determination Theory. *Computers in Human Behavior*. 26(4):741–752. doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2010.01.011.
- Chiu, TKF. 2022. Applying the Self-Determination Theory (SDT) to Explain Student Engagement in Online Learning during the Covid-19 Pandemic. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*. 54(1):14–30. doi.org/10.1080/15391523.2021.1891998.
- Deci, EL & Ryan, RM. 2000. The “What” and “Why” of Goal Pursuits: Human Needs and the Self-Determination of Behavior. *Psychological Inquiry*. 11(4):227–268. doi.org/10.1207/S15327965PLI1104_01.
- Hsu, HCK, Wang, CV & Levesque-Bristol, C. 2019. Reexamining the Impact of Self-Determination Theory on Learning Outcomes in the Online Learning Environment. *Education and Information Technologies*. 24(3):2159–2174. doi.org/10.1007/s10639-019-09863-w.
- Ikahihifo, T.B., Kerr, T.B., Graham, C.R., Larsen, R.A., Kimmons, R.M., Leary, H.M. and Fischer, L., 2019. *Self-Determination Theory and Student Emotional Engagement in Self-Determination Theory and Student Emotional Engagement in Higher Education Higher Education*.
- Imane Messaoudi & Sana Sakale. 2024. Interpersonal Skills: A Gateway to Emotional Intelligence in the Workplace. *International Journal of English Language Studies*. 6(2):172–176. doi.org/10.32996/ijels.2024.6.2.25.
- Jeno, L.M., 2015. *Encouraging Active Learning in Higher Education: A Self-Determination Theory Perspective*.

- Johansen, M.O., Eliassen, S. and Jenö, L.M., 2023. *The bright and dark side of autonomy: How autonomy support and thwarting relate to student motivation and academic functioning*. Frontiers Media SA.
- Kaushik, DrR & Sinsinwar, DrJ. 2024. Significance of Soft Skills in Career Development. *International Journal of English Literature and Social Sciences*. 9(1):271–275. doi.org/10.22161/ijels.91.35.
- Khan, IU, Hameed, Z, Yu, Y, Islam, T, Sheikh, Z & Khan, SU. 2018. Predicting the Acceptance of MOOCs in a Developing Country: Application of Task-Technology Fit Model, Social Motivation, and Self-Determination Theory. *Telematics and Informatics*. 35(4):964–978. doi.org/10.1016/j.tele.2017.09.009.
- Li, H., Peng, M.Y., Yang, M. and Chen, C., 2020. *Exploring the Influence of Learning Motivation and Socioeconomic Status on College Students' Learning Outcomes Using Self-Determination Theory*. Frontiers Media SA.
- Lozano-Jiménez, J.E., Huéscar, E. and Moreno-Murcia, J.A., 2021. *From Autonomy Support and Grit to Satisfaction With Life Through Self-Determined Motivation and Group Cohesion in Higher Education*. Frontiers Media SA.
- Magaldi, D & Berler, M. 2020. Semi-structured Interviews. doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-24612-3_857.
- Pineda, D, Lozano-Jimenez, JE & Moreno-Murcia, JA. 2024. Autonomy support in higher education: a key strategy for the well-being of university students. *F1000Research*. 13:839. doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.144803.1.
- Rotar, O. 2022. Online student support: a framework for embedding support interventions into the online learning cycle. *Open Access*. (10.1186/s41039-021-00178-4). doi.org/10.1186/s41039-021-00178-4.
- Ryan, RM & Deci, EL. 2000. Self-Determination Theory and the Facilitation of Intrinsic Motivation, Social Development, and Well-being. *American Psychologist*. 55(1):68–78. doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.55.1.68.
- Ryan, RM & Deci, EL. 2020. Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation from a self-determination theory perspective: Definitions, theory, practices, and future directions Richard M. Ryan & Edward L. Deci. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*. 61. doi.org/10.1016/j.cedpsych.2020.101860.
- Vansteenkiste, M, Aelterman, N, De Muijnck, GJ, Haerens, L, Patall, E & Reeve, J. 2018. Fostering Personal Meaning and Self-Relevance: A Self-Determination Theory Perspective on Internalization. *Journal of Experimental Education*. 86(1):30–49.
- Wisniewski, T., White, C., Green, C., Elder, A. F., Sohel, S., Perry, N. E., & Shapka, J. D. (2018). *Supporting Students through Role Redefinition: A Self-Determination Theory Perspective*. UNISA Press. 10.25159/1947-9417/3700
- Zak-Moskal, A. D., & Garrison, M. J. (2021). *The New York Journal of Student Affairs The New York Journal of Student Affairs*